

JOB SATISFACTION AND ITS EFFECT OF EMPLOYEES IN ROOTS INDUSTRIES INDIA, COIMBATORE

S. Selvin*, P. T. J. K. Lilian & Dr. B. Velmurugan*****

* PG Scholar, Department of Management Studies, NPR College of Engineering & Technology, Dindigul, Tamilnadu

** Assistant Professor, Department of Management Studies, NPR College of Engineering & Technology, Dindigul, Tamilnadu

*** Associate Professor & HOD, Department of Management Studies, NPR College of Engineering & Technology, Dindigul, Tamilnadu

Cite This Article: S. Selvin, P. T. J. K. Lilian & Dr. B. Velmurugan, “Job Satisfaction and Its Effect of Employees in Roots Industries India, Coimbatore”, International Journal of Scientific Research and Modern Education, Volume 8, Issue 1, Page Number 95-98, 2023.

Copy Right: © IJSRME, 2023 (All Rights Reserved). This is an Open Access Article distributed under the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

Abstract:

The study examines different aspects of job satisfaction like culture, leadership communication, commitment, job content, training, rewards and recognition opportunities, teamwork, superior subordinate relationship and delegation, at Roots Industries, Coimbatore. The research done is descriptive study involving survey and enquiry. The tools used for the data collection are questionnaires interviews and observations. The sampling design used is random sampling Sample of 103 employees from study population of 248 was taken. The secondary was collected from the company’s manuals, employee handbook, intranet and website. The research was carried out for a period of 4 months. The analysis was carried on a software SPSS and stated satisfaction level of different parameters. The overall job satisfaction showed people were satisfied with their current job but still measures should to be taken to improve the satisfaction level.

Key Words: Job Satisfaction, Job Content, Teamwork, Commitment

Introduction:

Attitudes are evaluative statements - either favourable or unfavourable - concerning objects, people or events. They reflect how one feels about something. Work Attitudes are the feelings and beliefs that largely determine how employees will perceive their environment, commit themselves to intended actions, and ultimately behave. Job Satisfaction is one of the many work related attitudes individuals hold like Job Involvement, Organizational Commitment, etc. Job Satisfaction thus is a set of favourable or unfavourable feelings and emotions with which employees view their work. A person with high level of job satisfaction holds positive feelings about the job, while a person who is dissatisfied with his/ her job holds negative feelings about the job. Job satisfaction is an important concern for both the employee as well as the employer as it has an impact on many organizational behaviours. The employees satisfaction is conducted to provide the information needed to improve various factors like productivity loyalty and job satisfaction. With the employee’s views, organizations can identify the root causes and create improvements. Organization just needs to discover what motivates the people, what drives loyalty and what genuinely makes the employees happy and employee remain satisfied only when they know their issued are being addressed.

Significance of the Study:

Roots Industries India Ltd. is a leading manufacturer of HORNS in India and the 11th largest Horn Manufacturing Company in the world. Headquartered in Coimbatore - India, ROOTS has been a dominant player in the manufacture of Horns and other products like Castings and Industrial Cleaning Machines. Since its establishment in 1970, ROOTS has had a vision and commitment to produce and deliver quality products adhering to International Standards. With a strong innovative base and commitment to Quality, Roots Industries India Limited has occupied a key position in both international and domestic market as suppliers to leading OEMs and after market. Similar to products, Roots has leading edge over competitor on strong quality system base. Now, RIL is the first Indian Company and first horn manufacturing company in the world to get ISO/TS16949 certification based on effective implementation of QS 9000 and VDA 6.1 system requirement earlier. RIL has entered into technical collaboration with Robert Bosch, SA to further enhance the technical competence. Roots' vision is to become a world-class company manufacturing world-class product, excelling in human relation. Roots Industries India Ltd electric horns currently holding 60% of the Indian Market Share. They are suppliers to leading automobile manufacturers such as Volkswagen, Toyota, Mercedes-Benz, Skoda, Navistar, Harley Davidson, Tata Motors, etc., are also the exclusive suppliers of the specialtype horns to defense. Their export market covers above 40 countries, which include United States, Japan, Germany, Russia, China, Italy and Africa, now the Roots has expended and concentrated on industrial cleaning machines

Roots Groups promoted by Mr. K. Ramasamy, A Master Degree holder in Automobile Engineering from Lincoln Technical Institute, USA, has its corporate office at Coimbatore in South India extending the philosophy of quality to all spheres of its activity in the market leader in India for flagship product automobile

horns. Roots single minded pursuit of enhancing the quality of life has led to many other diversifications. Roots today is a multi-faced corporate entity with interests in auto mobile accessories cleaning equipment, castings, precision tools, hi-tech engineering services, healthcare & education.

Review of Literature:

Denton, The literature on employee retention clearly explains that satisfied employees who are happy with their jobs are more devoted for doing a good job and look forward to improve their organizational customers' satisfaction (Denton 2010).

Mobley Employees who are satisfied have higher intentions of persisting with their organization, which results in a decreased turnover rate (Mobley et al., 2019).

Anderson & Sullivan abundant studies have hypothesized and empirically validated the link between satisfaction and behavioral intentions and behaviours such as employee's retention (Anderson & Sullivan, 2013). Further, numerous studies explain the importance of high employees' involvement and how it could enhance their retention (Arthur 1994). In summary, the literature defines retention as continuing relation between employees

Yuan-Ho Chen (2018) Research study on Employee's satisfaction and happiness of companies with different cultural managements had revealed many interesting and significant outcome. Survey questionnaires exquisitely designed and specialized in employee's satisfaction, happiness and job commitment were used and focused in this study

Alexandru Mihalcea et.al (2021) Satisfaction is a frequently used construct studied in the organizational psychology, being considered to have a direct influence on the working quality of the employees' of an organization. The leader's personality does not only impact the performance, but also the job satisfaction of the subordinates. The present study proposes to verify three hypothesis: 1. Showing the connection between different sides of job satisfaction and personality profile of the subjects with leading positions 2. Evaluating the efficiency of a certain coaching type addressed to top managers by analyzing the level of satisfaction of their subordinates and 3. Identifying personality traits specific to leaders who generate satisfaction among their team.

Objectives of the Study:

- To measure the employees job satisfaction level in Roots Industries India Limited
- To measure the level of job satisfaction among employee.
- To study and analyze the various factors that are affecting the employees satisfaction level.
- To locate and analyze specific areas which provide reasonable level of satisfaction
- To understand the problem of the employees and their working conditions.
- To evaluate the relationship between managers and coworkers

Hypothesis of the Study:

- Satisfied employees tend to perform more efficiently at work place as compared to dissatisfied employees
- Type of occupation affects the satisfaction level of employees

Research Design and Methodology:

Research is a systematic method of finding solutions to problems. It is essentially an investigation, a recording and an analysis of evidence for the purpose of gaining knowledge.

"Research comprises of defining and redefining problem, formulating hypothesis or suggested solutions, collecting, organizing and evaluating data, reaching conclusions, testing conclusion to determine whether they fit the formulated hypothesis.

The research design used in this project is descriptive in nature. The descriptive research is study in an attempt to obtain all relevant and accurate descriptive of the situation.

A descriptive study is designed to describe details of the problem. Descriptive research includes surveys and fact findings enquiries of different kinds.

Data Collection Methods:

Primary Data:

Primary data is the data that is collected by researchers themselves during their own research using research tools such as experiments, survey questionnaires, interviews, and observation. In this study the primary data were collected from the employees of Roots Industries India Limited through questionnaire.

Secondary Data:

The Secondary data is the data that are gathered from the studies, surveys, or experiments that have been run by other people or for another research. In this study the secondary data were collected from books, journals, and websites.

Tools Used for Data Collection:

Among the various methods, which can be used to collect the Primary Data, the researcher has adopted Questionnaire method. The researcher has prepared structured questionnaires, which contained predominantly multiple choice questions. The respondent's opinion is gathered with regard to the problem with the help of the Questionnaire.

Data Analysis and Interpretation:

Chart 1: Distribution of Respondents by Satisfaction about Salary

The above table clearly shows that as we can observe in the Bar chart 57% of the Blue collar employees are satisfied about their salary and 19% of employees are fully satisfied. 15% of employees partially satisfied and 9% employees are dissatisfied.

Chart 2: Distribution of Respondents by Nature of Work

Nature of work is an important determinant of job satisfaction and the question worked a very favorable response. 77% are satisfied and 16% are fully satisfied and remaining 7% are partially satisfied with their nature of work.

Suggestions:

- Pay scale for employees shall be revising done.
- Welfare activities like Management’s loan facilities, housing facilities, counseling for family related categories must be improved.
- Canteen facilities should be improved.
- Transport facilities should be improved.
- Loan facilities should be improved.
- Career counseling programmes must be improved.

Conclusion:

Job satisfaction is a measure of how much employees enjoy their jobs. Employees who are very satisfied with their jobs will perform their jobs in a very different manner than employees who actively dislike their jobs. Employees are the organization's most valuable asset, and they must be satisfied in order to improve

their performance. Companies with satisfied employees see higher overall profits because a large portion of their workforce is more motivated and productive. The overall satisfaction level of the employees is 90.01%. Hence, the company concentrates on the remaining 10% to get 100% satisfaction level.

References:

1. Company Reports (Annual Report).
2. By Robert H. Hollier “The Distribution of Spare Parts”.
3. By Velury Vijay Bhasker “Indian Auto Component Industry
4. Decade of Growth and Way Forward”.